

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

REVISED BLOOM IN TEACHER EDUCATION: AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS

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ABSTRACT

In study, an assessment tool based on Revised Bloom's taxonomy to help organic chemistry educators better align their assessments with teaching activities and to help future chemistry teachers improve their learning and metacognition skills was developed. The paper shows ways to improve the teaching and learning of students in organic chemistry, on the example of aromatic hydrocarbons, thereby adjusting teaching and improving students' mastery of the material, developing questions at higher levels of cognitive skills, and assisting students in preparing for exams. In addition, methodological guidelines have been developed to help teachers in creating high-quality lesson materials at the appropriate level of taxonomy. It was established that teaching with revised Bloom's taxonomy effectively develops students' understanding, basic knowledge, and self-study capacity. The topic "Aromatics" which is detailed in the research was built by studying the content characteristics of organic chemistry. We conclude that it is suitable to develop the revised Bloom's taxonomy-based methodology for other organic chemistry topics.

Keywords: aromatics, Bloom, revised Bloom, taxonomy, organic chemistry, education, teaching.

Introduction

Natural science education is the most important aspect of the country's development process. And that is why countries where the process of technological and scientific progress is just beginning primarily direct their resources to the field of education (Demirci & Mutlu, 2017). Scientific literacy mobilizes all cognitive, affective, psychomotor capabilities to understand, track, and regularly actively apply scientific and technological concepts in their activities (Hastürk, 2017). Science courses have the potential to cultivate citizenship competencies (Kus & Mert, 2017). In this aspect, the requirements for future-oriented science education and teacher education including deeper learning and critical thinking skills, cross-curricular work, education for sustainable development, and research-based teacher education comes to the forefront (Mork et al., 2021)

Chemistry itself is the most difficult subject for students, while the greatest difficulties are caused by the course of organic chemistry and its individual topics. (Ochonogor, 2020, Akman et al., 2023). Students acquainted with the introductory organic chemistry with a certain amount of apprehension, usually as a result of rumors from older students who have found ways to negotiate a course. Unfortunately, some students view organic chemistry as more than a rite of passage or the academic equivalent of hazing. Students just need to linger on the trip and hope that they remember enough to complete the course. At this point, most organic chemistry teachers are concerned that students are mostly trying to just memorize the material rather than understand it (Pungente & Badger, 2003).

Literature Review

When studying the literature, it was revealed that many studies are devoted to the stable problems of teaching organic chemistry (O'Dwyer & Childs, 2017, Cook et al., 2013,). Most authors emphasize that the difficulties are mainly related to the topics in which it is necessary to represent organic compounds, the study of their properties, aromaticity, nomenclature and, of course, the mechanisms of organic reactions (Lorenzo, et al., 2012). The subjects' responses highlight difficulties related to specific contents, such as conformation and spatial visualization of molecules, stereochemistry, and reaction mechanisms; lack of concepts from High School; and individual habits and characteristics of teachers, students, or both, such as didactics, concentration, and engagement. The results report on the importance of rethinking strategies and methodologies in the context of Organic Chemistry I in Higher Education (Alves et al., 2021). Professional teacher could assess the knowledge and skills by asking to demonstrate those skills in action, in other words, by doing something that is observable and measurable (Adams, 2015).

Although the importance of chemistry is indisputable, organic chemistry has been reported widely by researchers and chemical educators as being difficult (Chang & Goldsby, 2016; Childs & Sheehan, 2009; Salame et al., 2019). Chemistry (for that matter organic chemistry) is often considered a difficult subject and this observation has repelled learners from progressing with their studies in chemistry (Salame et al., 2019; Si-bomana et al., 2021; Alves, 2021).

So, development of critical thinking skills is main aspect of improvement of effective communication skills and knowledge of students. Modern teachers

must develop effective lesson plans and assessment tools to achieve it and devise educational materials also to achieve educational goals (Nurmatova & Altun, 2023).

Taxonomy is the science of classifying complex hierarchical systems, in other words, organizing objects from the lowest to the highest. It is often depicted as a tree-like structure or pyramid. In the middle of the XX century, taxonomy began to be used in the field of education. In 1956, scientists at the University of Chicago, led by psychologist Benjamin Bloom, developed Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom, 1956) that defined taxonomies for learning in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor.

Bloom's taxonomy is pedagogical system that provides structurization of educational process, measure and evaluate knowledge and skills of students. (Kathwool & Bloom, 1964, Dong, 2014, Muzaqalieva, 2015). According to Bloom, taxonomy is system that was supposed to eliminate the existing inconsistencies in education between the goals of the curriculum, the opportunities it provides, and the actual learning outcomes (Muzaqalieva, 2015). Bloom's idea is elimination the existing inconsistencies in education between the goals of the curriculum, the opportunities it provides, and the actual learning outcomes. The essence of Bloom's taxonomy is that it breaks down the educational process into separate stages or levels that a student must overcome to master the educational material. Each stage represents a specific learning goal and includes specific actions to achieve that goal. All educational goals are arranged in a hierarchical order, which means that they need to be mastered sequentially - from simple to complex. This approach helps to track results through the achievement of goals and turns learning into a process aimed at solving specific tasks one by one.

A taxonomy of educational goals is a convenient methodology that helps measure learning outcomes through the achievement of specific goals. This system is used to organize the educational process around the world.

Instructors can plan lessons and design courses according to the taxonomy when clear, measurable, and time-bound learning goals need to be set. This allows the student to focus on a specific task at the moment, and the teacher to make the learning process consistent and structure the program (Sahu, 2021). In addition, Bloom's taxonomy helps to assess the quality of education in general (Bloom et al., 1956). To do this, educators can choose appropriate ways to measure student outcomes based on their level (Bloom et al., 1956)

Almost half a century later the cognitive domain taxonomy was revised (Anderson et al., 2000) to reflect more active thinking and improve usability by adding verbs to describe levels.

There is a limited amount of work in the literature on the application of Bloom's taxonomy to various fields of science. For example, in the field of math (Kacovsky et al., 2022), biology (Mandikonza, 2024; Nagci, 2018), computer science education (Ulum, 2016; Rodrigues et al. 2017; Ullah et al., 2020) and chemistry (Asmussen et al., 2023; Bravo-Gomez et al,

2023, Kaneza et al, 2024; Shaw, 2023, Pungente et al., 2003), etc. However, given the teaching effectiveness you have indicated in these works, as well as the works on Bloom's original and revised taxonomy, the development of tactics for teaching certain topics of organic chemistry that would be based on Bloom's hierarchy is relevant. This work is the first in a series of papers devoted to the application of Bloom's updated taxonomy in teaching chemistry.

This article presents case of implementing Bloom's Taxonomy for preservice teachers in the organic chemistry course when teaching topic "Aromatics" in high school. The article also aims to explore the benefits and limitations of integrating the taxonomy into the organic chemistry classroom and determine its role in designing instructional approaches that can significantly enhance the quality of organic chemistry classes for modern teachers. Furthermore, this article intends to offer essential guidelines and recommendations and valuable insights from existing literature regarding the proper implementation of Bloom's Taxonomy for educators.

The main aim of the study is development of system-structural approach based on revised Bloom's taxonomy for teaching organic chemistry in high school and prepare the structural model for the course "Organic Chemistry" consisting of graphs and subgraph of the main sections of the program for students of science specialties.

Research Questions/Objectives

The questions of presented study are as follows:

1. May Bloom's taxonomy help organic chemistry tutors build their lesson plans for development higher-order thinking abilities of students?
2. Can organic chemistry teachers develop the required skills in students by gradually integrating the six stages of the revised Bloom's taxonomy into their lesson plan objectives?
3. What is the relation between Revised Bloom's taxonomy and critical mind of learners?

Participants

The current work reports the implementation of revised Bloom's in Baku State University in the 2023-2024 academic year. It was used to support a one-month module regarding Organic chemistry. 24 students of the second year of bachelors took part in study. 8 of 24 were male, 16 were female students. 12 Students of experimental classes took turns to educate using revised Bloom's taxonomy. The topic was "Aromatics". To be consistent with the research content, pre- and post-impact test design was selected. The development of the study capacity of students was assessed by the teacher and by students themselves.

Methodology

Experimental data to conclude the effectiveness of teaching using revised Bloom's taxonomy were processed and analyzed with Microsoft Excel software. The research process was conducted through the following levels:

Level 1: Choosing topic: analysis content of lessons in the program of Organic chemistry course

Level 2: Identification the problems in content or questions that students need to solve to be solved by using revised Bloom

Level 3: Prepare lectures and didactic materials, organization of individual work of students by using informational sites and design guidelines for students that correspond to the problems to be solved

Level 4: Consultation with expert-teachers who are chemistry lecturers, professors at Baku State University

Level 5: Get feedback from students in the test to continue to edit and perfect methodology.

The strength of the teaching effects depends directly on how the educational process is organized, which is based on the knowledge of the psychological and age characteristics of the students.

The application of age-appropriate methods and pedagogical approaches serves the student's creative self-development through cognitive initiative to high motivation learning. The main task of high school is to form a system of universal skills, abilities of students for independent activity.

To improve the quality of knowledge of students, it is necessary to systematically carry out a diagnosis of

students' knowledge and skills, to know the level of individual achievements of each student. To achieve these goals, we combine individual and group forms in class and in extracurricular activities. To be successful in presented study work we used pedagogical technologies built on revised Bloom's taxonomy. The Organic Chemistry course of bachelors' contain abstract concepts that is hard to teach and to learn. Therefore, this knowledge is suitable for organizing students' study and self-study using various teaching methods. But effective organization of teaching process and goals achievement is quietly problematic.

The problem is that at present the methodological developments for conducting interactive classes at the university are mainly aimed at organizing the work of students in the classroom, while the issue of using interactive methods in the independent work of students does not have a deep pedagogical and methodological study.

Traditional technology has some disadvantages that are not suitable for individualizing the learning process: a focus on memory rather than thought does little to promote creativity (Table 1).

Table 1.

Traditional teaching "Aromatics"

Levels	The status of implementation
Learning new topic	Structure of benzene. Kekule formula. Molecular orbitals of benzene. Aromaticity. Huckel's rule. Condensed aromatics. Heterocyclic aromatics. Electrophilic substitution reactions. Generalized misconceptions on reaction mechanisms. Misconceptions on sigma- and pi-complexes. Influence of substituents on rate and direction of electrophilic substitution. Complementary and non-complementary orientation. Nitration agents and mechanism of nitration reaction of aromatics. Nitration of biphenyl, naphthalene and other arenes. Halogenation agents and mechanism of halogenation reaction of aromatics. Sulphonating agents and mechanism of sulphonation reaction of aromatics. Alkylation agents and Friedel-Crafts alkylation of arenes. Acylation agents and mechanism of acylation of arenes. Gatterman-Koch formylation and other similar reaction. Wurtz-Fittig and other reactions of cross-coupling. Catalytic hydration of arenes and Birch's reduction of arenes. Oxidation of alkylbenzene to carboxylic acids. Misconceptions on S_{N1} and S_{N2} and S_{NAr} . Mechanism of addition-elimination, examples of reactions, activating influence of electronwithdrawing substituents. Meyzenheimer's anionic complexes.
Reinforce the topic's focus	Practice on topic (answer the questions, discussion, laboratory work, practical lessons)
Control	Problem solving (colloquium)
Evaluation	Evaluation by task value

The Most Typical tasks are: insert, highlight, memorize, reproduce, decide by example, etc. The lesson is carried out only the initial orientation on the material, and achieving high results is left to the homework. Therefore, the updated educational program covers the traditional functions of the educational

normative document, which describes innovative pedagogical approaches to the organization of the educational process in modern school. Teaching methods are the main guidelines in the construction of a fundamentally new structure of the curriculum in the discipline. One of the main features of the updated curriculum is the Revised Taxonomy of Benjamin Bloom's (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Revised Bloom's taxonomy

Bloom's revised taxonomy is an updated and expanded version that was developed by David Krutool and Laura Anderson in 2001. This revised version was created to more accurately reflect modern educational practices and the inclusion of a wider range of skills, including digital and information skills. The revised taxonomy becomes more complex, knowledge is highlighted in dimension, and the nouns in the names of skill categories are replaced by Verbs. This allows us to better characterize the depth and breadth of each

category and answers the question "what should a student be able to do after achieving the result? training?" In addition, the category of synthesis was swapped with the score and was Renamed to "Create".

The purpose of this work is to comprehend and generalize the methodological experience of the Department of Organic Chemistry of on the use of interactive teaching methods for the organization of independent work of students in the study of chemical disciplines (Table 2).

Table 2.

Revised Bloom's taxonomy in teaching chemistry

Levels	General Description	Thematic description	Teacher activity	Student activity	Main verbs for activity
Remember	Selection and remembering of information	Classification of organic compounds according to reaction centers and functional groups	Explains, guides	Remembers, perceives	Remember, Name, list
Understanding	Understanding the information, self-formulation of problem	Influence of structure of compound on its properties	Compares, demonstrates	Explains, demonstrates	Story, explain, discuss, discover, draw
Apply	Using concepts in various situations and objects	Describes the mechanism of interactions	Observes, helps, criticizes	Solves problems, presents knowledge	Use, study, carry out, interpret, choose, classify, determine, change, modify, show, solve, find
Analyze	Devison of information on bonded parts	Analyse situations and compare antagonist ideas	Guides, informs, studies	Analyzes, discusses, reveals	Analyze, evaluate, group, calculate, compare, discuss, differ, study, classify, choose, find, check
Evaluate	Elvaluation using criteria	Prognose physical, chemical and physiological properties of compound using structure information	Classifies, allows, evaluates	Discusses, evaluates, chooses	Argument, choose, Prove, conclude, explain, select, support, prognose, measure
Create	Compilation of information	Creation of new organic molecules, synthesis of compounds by various ways	Summarizes, evaluates	Summarizes, plans, formulates	Group, collect, combine, compose, summarize, invent, modify, organize, prepare, establish, think, replace

Realized Learning activities for students in Aromatics presented in table 3.

Table 3.

Extended representation of Learning activities for students in revised Bloom's taxonomy in Aromatics

Revised Bloom's level	Individual activity	Group activity
Remember	Read the lecture texts and e-books on topic Write out lecture abstracts Draw structures of aromatics Identify aromatics Classify aromatics Quiz yourself using ICT List resources of aromatics	Check each others aromatics structure drawings Ask the questions Answer the questions
Understanding	Report the structure of aromatics by using own words Gives examples Describes the influence ED and EW groups to the electron density allocation by own words	Dispute about the content Practice to show the effects of substituents by drawing Point out the mistakes of each other
Apply	Answer the question: How variation of substituent effects on compound's activity	Practice by solving problems on topic Implement mechanism of electrophilic substitution to reactions with various reagents
Analyze	Search and study modern literature on topic Compare the tutor's interpretation with own Define relationship between other hydrocarbon classes	Work-in-pairs on study of modern literature on topic Work-in-pairs in identification of relationship between main concepts on topic
Evaluate	Provide self-evaluation	Carry out the assessment of strong and weak sides of groupmates on the bases of evaluation criteria
Create	Generate a hypothesis of problems Create a study levels Prepare a problem solving algorithm	Work-in-groups on solving hard-level problems on aromatics Evaluate the strong and weak parts of groupmates work Critically assess each other

Findings and Discussion

Taxonomy plays an important role in learning theory. It is important because it allows: to set goals in learning correctly; select assessment tools that are adequate to the set goals; correctly reflect on the results of learning, i.e. establish what difficulties students have experienced when studying this or that material. In order to ensure the formation of high-level thinking skills in the lessons of special disciplines, the teacher should adhere to the following recommendations: - Test questions should cover all 6 levels of taxonomy - In the formulation of questions for each level, we use verbs-actions, they will help to assess the depth of knowledge of the student - if the student does not cope with a group of questions at one of the levels, then you should not continue testing - if he has not realized the new information, then he will not be able to use it in practice, it is better to redirect the student to repeat the material and ask him to take the test again - to provide an understanding of what thinking skills students need - to teach the art of argumentation, to teach to evaluate the results of their activities.

Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy aims to provide practical assistance to the modern educator who is aware of the importance of high-level thinking in modern education.

When composing questions on Remember, the words-questions are often used: when, what is, who, is

it true, etc. The load is not on thinking, but on memory, for example, what is halogenation? The student simply remembers and recognizes information.

At the Understanding level, there is an understanding of the information received; formulating the problem in your own words. The student explains, transforms, i.e. information is processed, for example, what is the difference between arenas and other unsaturated hydrocarbons?

Apply means the use of concepts in new situations. Questions on Apply allow you to transfer what you have learned to new conditions, for example, to solve problems, for example, predict the result of the Friedel-Crafts alkylation reaction, what are the possible results of halogenation of benzene in the presence of Lewis acids and in the presence of light.

At the Analyze level, information is broken down into related parts. Questions for analysis require clarification of causes and effects, separation of individual parts from the whole, for example, what is the essence of the problem, what conclusion can be drawn, what are the prerequisites, etc.?. The analysis makes it possible to understand and show how it works. At the Evaluate level, the learner discusses, chooses and evaluates using certain criteria. At this level, verbs are more often used: prove, choose those, compare, draw a conclusion,

substantiate, predict. For example, prove that the aromatic 6pi-system is the cause of benzene's excessive stability.

Create is a compilation of information. The questions on create are all about creative problem solving. It is not enough just to have the available information. It is necessary to create a new whole on the basis of an original approach. At this level, verbs are more often used: develop, formulate, generalize, combine, modify, etc. For example, summarize the ideas about cross-coupling reactions.

A very important point is teaching students to independently formulate multi-level questions when performing tasks individually. Then, using taxonomy, students will be able not only to answer questions, but also to develop certain types of questions that allow them to reveal each block of Bloom's pyramid. This principle is not characteristic of the traditional education system, since it was more common there when only teachers form questions and ask them.

The use of this method will allow the teacher to diagnose the quality of the knowledge gained. Too "theoretical" education does not allow students to form high-quality knowledge. But knowledge that has no connection with practice causes a one-sided and very narrow understanding of the issue under study. Additional motivation of students aimed at activating answers to more complex questions is possible with a differentiated system of evaluating answers to questions. A distinctive feature of this form of organization of the

educational process is the fact that students receive all the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities not in the process of studying a particular discipline, but in the process of working on a particular project. The project method can be defined as a way of learning through a detailed development of a problem, which should end with a very real, tangible practical result that has a real life context. In the educational process of a university, a project is understood as a set of actions specially organized by a teacher and independently performed by students, culminating in the creation of a creative product.

For experimental sciences, the use of the project method is very relevant. For students of the Faculty of Chemistry, as a project assignment in the discipline "Organic Chemistry", a research project has been developed on the topic: "Study of the properties of aromatic hydrocarbons". Such projects, as a rule, are group projects. The use of the project method allows you to acquire not only professional knowledge, skills and abilities, but also helps to form such competencies as the ability to search, collect and analyze information. Among other things, the project method allows you to form such personal qualities as the ability to work in a team, take responsibility for the choice, analyze the results of activities, and feel like a member of a group. Thus, by applying various teaching methods, it is possible to significantly improve the quality of education (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Implementation of Revised Bloom to laboratory work

Revised Bloom's taxonomy aims to provide practical assistance to the modern educator who is aware of the importance of high-level thinking in modern education.

Critical mind plays an important role in mastering each of the levels of the taxonomy of chemistry educational goals. It allows students not only to memorize and reproduce information, but also to analyze it, compare, highlight key points and develop critical conclusions. An important characteristic of critical mind is the ability to ask questions, identify, assess the reliability of sources of information, and make true decisions (Taagepera, 2000).

We observed main intersection between Bloom's taxonomy and critical mind: enrichment of the educational process - Bloom's revised taxonomy provides a structured path for the development of students' cognitive skills. Critical thinking is key to unlocking the higher levels of this taxonomy. Teaching students to analyze, evaluate, and create information stimulates deep and productive learning; critical mind and Bloom's revised taxonomy levels provide students with the necessary tools to succeed in their future careers.

Critical mind also helps students develop self-awareness and self-regulation skills. They can control their learning process, as well as their thinking and behavioral habits. Critical mind will also come in handy for teachers when solving complex problems that may arise in a learning environment. As a result, the development of critical mind in future teachers and chemists not only enriches their professional skills, but also contributes to a better education of students. Teachers with this skill can better adapt to change, inspire students to learn actively, and successfully address the challenges they face in their work.

The knowledge of the organic chemistry of hydrocarbons, especially Aromatics at high school is very difficult and includes hard abstract concepts, that is the key to wholly understand the scientific material. Considering that it is chain and interdependent process the small weakness in one link results big problems in perception of whole material. According to experts' assessment of proposed study, the revised Bloom's taxonomy implemented in organic chemistry course is suitable for the curriculum and teaching conditions at high schools in Azerbaijan (Table 3, Fig.2).

Table 3.

Evaluation of knowledge of Experimental Group (EG) learners. (For Remember and Understanding 0, 0.5 and 1 points; for apply, Analysis, Evaluate and Create 0, 1 and 2 points)

Levels	Learners of EG											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Remember	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Understanding	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Apply	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
Analysis	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Evaluate	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	1	2	1	2
Create	0	1	1	0	2	1	0	2	1	1	2	1
Total points	6	8	7	7	10	8	6	10	8	9	9	8

Figure 3. Comparison of educational results of Control (CG) and Experimental Groups (EG)

The teachers participating in the experiment gave positive feedback in using revised Bloom's taxonomy. Based on their mind, the organization of teaching and learning according to the revised Bloom helped students conduct their self-evaluation and group-activities. Teachers provide timely and effective help for each student and better control and evaluate students. The interaction between students in the group increased teaching results and students' self-study ability, develop knowledge and skills. Thus, the positive feedback of both teachers and students also confirmed effectiveness of applying revised Bloom to teach topic.

Implications

The following recommendations were prepared by us as research results:

(1) It is advisable to continue to promote research to expand the application scope of Revised Bloom's taxonomy in teaching organic chemistry according to the other contents of the Organic Chemistry subject.

(2) High schools in Azerbaijan need to focus on promotion in building facilities, support and encourage teachers in using Revised Bloom's taxonomy

(3) the combination of critical thinking and Bloom's revised taxonomy plays an important role in modern education: it contributes to the development of students as independent thinkers, preparing them for successful careers and active citizenship in a complex and global world.

Conclusion

The trend of applying revised Bloom's taxonomy in teaching organic chemistry hasn't been increasingly evident globally. Still, we conclude that it creates good conditions for the formation of basic knowledge and understanding which is the essential mission of every tutor. Teaching by using revised Bloom's taxonomy is helping to achieve all educating goals and carry out the control on every level of process. The Organic Chemistry section in the program of Baku State University has much content related to international science. Teaching with revised Bloom's taxonomy effectively develops students' understanding, basic knowledge, and self-study capacity. The topic "Aromatics" which is detailed in the research was built by studying the content characteristics of organic chemistry. We conclude that it is suitable to develop the revised Bloom's taxonomy-based methodology for other organic chemistry topics.

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